

A Sogdian Zoroastrian Epitaph

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The group in question comprises Sogdian merchants in 6th century Chang'an, whose tomb monuments display Zoroastrian motifs. Several such monuments are funerary beds, with panels on the inside faces depicting the life of the deceased merchant; the tomb under review here is a sarcophagus in the shape of a Chinese-style house, with biographic panels along the outside walls. Sogdian traders had been travelling along the so-called Silk Roads to China and India since at least the 3rd century CE, and established themselves in several oasis cities along both the northern and southern routes. Not all were Zoroastrian; iconography and textual materials from various sites also indicate that some were Buddhist, Manichaean or "Nestorian" Christian. Wirkak's sarcophagus includes pictorial themes that could also relate to Buddhist and/or Manichaean ideology. The judgment scene on the eastern wall appears, however, to be definitively "Sogdian Zoroastrian," with some Chinese aesthetic elements. Reference to the couple going on to "the best existence" in the epitaph confirms this reading. Other tombs from a similar period belonging to Sogdian elite (several identified as "sabao" - that is a Sogdian community leader in a Chinese city) also indicate the Sogdian adaptation of disposal of the (excarinated, dried) bones in a carved ossuary to local Chinese burial practice.

Date Range: 494 CE - 579 CE

Region: Chang'an, Kachan/Liangzhou, and Kish

Region tags: China, Northern Zhou

These regions are all mentioned in the epitaph. Chang'an at this time was part of the Northern Zhou. Chang'an is located in modern-day Xi'an and Kish is located in modern-day Shakhrisabz in Uzbekistan.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yutaka Yoshida, "The Sogdian version of the new Xi'an inscription." In Etienne de la Vaissière and Eric Trombert, eds., *Les sogdiens en Chine* (Paris: Ecole Française d'Extrême Orient, 2005) ; 57-72.
- Source 2: Albert Dien, "Observations Concerning the Tomb of Master Shi." BAI 17 (2003)
- Source 3: Frantz Grenet, "More Zoroastrian Scenes on the Wirkak (Shi Jun) Sarcophagus." BAI 27 (2013 [2017]); 1-12.

Notes: See also: Frantz Grenet. 'Religious Diversity among Sogdian Merchants in Sixth-Century China: Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Manichaeism and Hinduism.' *Comparative Studies of South Asia, Africa and the Middle East* 27/2 (2007); 463-478. Zsuzsanna Gulácsi and Jason BeDuhn. 'The Religion of Wirkak and Wiyusi: The Zoroastrian Iconographic Program on a Sogdian Sarcophagus from Sixth-Century Xi'an.' BAI

26 (2012 [2016]); 1-32. Yang Junkai, "Carvings on the Stone Outer Coffin of Lord Shi of the Northern Zhou." In de la Vaissière and Trombert, eds. *Les soldats en Chine*; 21-39 (see full reference under Yoshida, above)
Jenny Rose. "Bird-Men and Other Hybrids: Some Central Asian Representations of Zoroastrian Yazatas." In Matteo Compareti, ed., *Fabulous Creatures and Spirits in Ancient Iranian Culture*. Bologna, 2018; 19-38.
Etienne de la Vaissière, 'Wirkak: Manichaeism, Zoroastrian or Khurrami? On Bilingualism and Syncretism in Sogdian Funerary Art.' *Studies on the Inner Asian Languages*, 30 (2015); 95-112.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Judith Lerner, "Zoroastrian Funerary Beliefs."
<https://edspace.american.edu/silkroadjournal/wp-content/uploads/sites/984/2017/09/Zoroastrian-Funerary-Beliefs.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Article on the Sogdian funerary monuments discovered in China in recent decades, which depict funerary rites and beliefs recognisable from Zoroastrian textual sources
- Source 1 URL: Nicholas Sims-Williams, "The Sogdian Epitaph of Shi Jun and his Wife."
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/bulletin-of-the-school-of-oriental-and-african-studies/article/sogdian-epitaph-of-shi-jun-and-his-wife/E8CBF0953D78B768D5E1E60D4A8BFADA>
- Source 1 Description: This article is a recent translation of the text, which varies somewhat from that of Yoshida, particularly regarding calendrical references.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: see note below

Notes: No collected online corpora of Sino-Sogdian texts exists. See Nicholas Sims-Williams (above) for references to translations of two other bilingual (Chinese-Middle Iranian) documents.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Notes: The epitaph appears to be etched

Method of inscription

- Other [specify]: Unknown

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Notes: The epitaph is on an oblong slate panel measuring 88 cm by 23 cm.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The slate was cut to fit the space above the door of the sarcophagus, and the text written vertically to fit onto the slate, with a line left blank on the right edge of the slate

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The two texts are not mutual translations.

Notes: The Chinese version of the text differs from the Sogdian. It is not clearly inscribed in places and omits some of the names and details in the Sogdian version, while presenting information not contained in the latter.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– Yes

↳ Cemetery

– Yes

Notes: The sarcophagus was in a burial chamber near the tombs of two other deceased Sogdians/ persons of Sogdian origin (named An Qie and Kang Ye).

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The location of the tomb near to two other Sogdian tombs suggests a cultural, possibly also religious, connection. The tomb of An Qie, another sabao (of Tongzhou) in the Northern Zhou era, also included an epitaph, and the lunette over the door to the burial chamber depicts similar Zoroastrian 'bird-priests' conducting funerary rites.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– Yes

Notes: The epitaph is on the lintel of the front of a Chinese-style house-shaped sarcophagus, which was placed in the centre of a single burial chamber .

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: This sarcophagus and other Sogdian funerary monuments in Xi'an of the period were found in shaft tombs, which were typically used in Chinese burials of the Northern Zhou period, with a passageway and, in the case of the tombs of Wirkak and An Qie, five airshafts.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

Notes: The epitaph is on the front of a stone sarcophagus which was buried in a shaft tomb. The sarcophagus is covered with pictorial reliefs relating to the life and death of the deceased. These were originally painted and gilded. Some scenes are biographical, but other panels appear to be religious in content. The interior walls of the sarcophagus were covered with red paintings of grapevines and leaves.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The four horses in two of the three panels on the eastern wall to are understood to symbolise Mithra's quadriga (Grenet 2013 [2017], 5). The two dogs are thought to represent those mentioned in Avestan text as guarding the Chinvat bridge (Videvdad. 13.9), and who accompany the daena (Videvdad. 19.30). The sea monsters are understood to symbolise the 'worst existence' (Pahlavi 'dushox' - hell).

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The figures of daena ('religion/'religious insight') and Vayu (Sogdian Weshparkar - the 'wind that is in the upper regions') on the east wall of the sarcophagus appear to be anthropomorphised respectively as a crowned woman (winged) and a man with a be-ribboned tiara, seated on a bull throne underneath two attendants with a billowing scarf. On a couple of other panels winged females/apsaras are depicted; in one scene, they rescue a man and a woman from a body of water. Two four-armed protector divinities guard the door of the tomb.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– Yes

Notes: The fire tended by the two Zoroastrian priests on the front façade of the sarcophagus is an emblem of Asha, the Amesha Spenta ('Life-giving Immortal'), whose name translate as "Order," "Right" or "Truth."

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: See note for "abstract symbol" above. The individual who lives an upright life is referred to as an 'ashawan' - a "follower of asha." Zoroastrian texts refer to the ashawan crossing the Chinvat bridge to the "best existence" (Avestan 'vahišta- ahu-'; Y. 46.10)

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: The woman receiving the scroll from Wirkak (usually identified as daena - the 'religion') and her two female attendants wear identical crowns. The two attendants carry a flower and a cup respectively. The daena has one hand on her kusti, the sacred cord around her waist. The divinity identified as Vayu sits cross-legged within a mandala on a throne of three bulls. Elsewhere on the sarcophagus, a preaching figure with a topknot, wearing a monk's robe over the left shoulder, and seated on a lotus base has been identified as either Mani or a Buddhist monk. The former identification is disputed (see Gulasci and Beduhn 2012 [2016], 6). This may portray the Zoroastrian soshyans (the final saviour) in the iconographic model of Maitreya (Grenet 2013 [2017], 2).

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The figures of Wirkak and Wikusi are prominent throughout the panels, appearing together with their sons in the first panel on the west wall, holding a baby in the second panel, and with one or two of their children crossing the bridge on the east wall. Other humans in scenes on the south, west and north walls include male and female musicians and servants, business colleagues, and hunting companion (see Yunkai 2005)..

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: The visual imagery of the crossing of the bridge and the welcome to the upper atmosphere replays the Zoroastrian textual narrative of the soul of the ashcan's transition to the 'best existence.' The water rescue by winged females may reflect a Manichaean or Buddhist narrative (on this, see Gulasci and Beduhn 2012 [2017], 10-11).

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: The panels depict biographical details of Wirkak's life, including both professional and personal events and activities, as well as his soul's journey into the afterlife.

↳ Specify

– Specify: The bird-priest image is associated with the Zoroastrian divine being (yazata) Sraosha

Notes: The figure of the priest with bird features (wings, feet and tail) seems to reflect the idea of the rooster, identified 'the assistant to Sraosha' (Avestan: sraoshāvarez), the Zoroastrian diving being whose name means "readiness to listen." In Avestan texts, the rooster presides over the pre-dawn watch of the night: its crowing announces the dawn, banishing the "demon of sloth" (see Yasna 57.16, Videvdad 18.14-16).

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably the epitaph was seen only by the transcriber(s), and the three sons of the deceased couple, who erected the tomb and sarcophagus. It may also have been seen by the priest(s) who conducted the funerary rituals and other family members present at such ritual.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: Sogdian Zoroastrianism differs from that in Sasanian Iran in the same timeframe, but, given the antiquity of the religion in the region of Sogdiana, does not seem to represent a "reformist" movement.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The epitaph is the earliest example of juxtaposed Chinese-Sogdian script.

Notes: The bilingual epitaph on the tomb of a Sogdian sabao - found in situ - is a key to understanding the import of the iconography on the sarcophagus. It also provides insight into the place of Sogdians in that period of Chinese history, and is an invaluable resource for the study of the Sogdian language. .

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Sogdian part of the epitaph contains some specific Zoroastrian terms, the most significant being a reference to the couple beginning life together in paradise at the same time. The Sogdian phrase translated as paradise, 'xwštm 'xw, is the equivalent of Avestan vahishta- ahu- (the 'best existence)

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The lineage is familial, not religious.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The lineage was one of official authority, not identifiably of religious authority. According to the Chinese version of the epitaph, Wirkak's grandfather was a a sabao 'in his own land', his father 'was equal' (Dien, 2013 [2017], 105). Wirkak's authority was as sabao. The sabao was a designated administrative official for the Sogdian community in the larger northern Chinese towns.. In the Tang period, the sabao had some supervision over Zoroastrian temples, but it is not known if he functioned in a priestly capacity.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Notes: The lineage is not religious but familial, noting that Wirkak/Shi Jun was of a family from Kish (near Shakhri Sabz in modern Uzbekistan).

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– No

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese epitaph speaks of the "suffused fragrance" of Wirkak/Shi Jun as enduring eternally, suggesting ontological distinction from the physical body. The Sogdian text implies a continuation of relationship between husband and wife in paradise, without specifying a spirit/body distinction.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The two spheres of existence - the thought world and the material world are acknowledged in the earliest Zoroastrian texts (Gathas). Modern Zoroastrians discuss the distinctions between approaches of the mind ('spiritual') and body ('material'), and the implications for conceptions of the afterlife.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: The Sogdian text refers to the 'best existence' (translated as 'paradise'), which, according to Zoroastrian eschatology was across and above the Chinvat Bridge. The Chinese text refers to the Way of Heaven as 'extensive and wide', and to the 'suffused fragrance' of Wirkak lasting for eternity (Dien 2013 [2017], 105).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Notes: See note for "above space." The reference to the vastness of the "way of heaven" in the Chinese account - a phrase reiterated on An Qie's epitaph - could denote the ordered universe, as well as 'heaven' (Chinese: tian)

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: That the soul of the ashawan goes to the 'best existence.'

Notes: Young Avestan texts (particularly Videvdad, Hadokht Nask) describe the judgment of the individual soul at death. Videvdad has injunctions as to the disposal of the corpse. Later texts outline the bodily resurrection of the dead and the reuniting with the soul before a final judgment.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Reincarnation

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

Notes: Both the Chinese and Sogdian texts state that the stone construction was built as a tomb for Wirkak and his wife by their three sons.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: In the iconography, particularly on the east wall, the couple appear to receive the blessings of the afterlife.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese version refers to the grandfather and father of Wirkak/Shi Jun as having virtue/admirable qualities

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: In the Chinese texts, both the father and grandfather of Wirkak/Shi Jun had characters that "shone".

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Both the Chinese and Sogdian texts trace the family lineage of Wirkak/Shi Jun through

his father and grandfather. Wirkak's sons are named in both texts as constructing the tomb 'for the sake of their father.'

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: In the Chinese epitaph, Wirkak/Shi Jun is described as of 'eminent distinction'

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: Both Chinese and Sogdian texts refer to Wirkak/Shi Jun and his family with phrases such as standing out, not of the ordinary, holding rank from the Emperor. The elaborate tomb chamber which held the sarcophagus also denotes Wirkak's elevated position in Chang'an..

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: The Sogdian text contains a long section concerning the notion of a couple living together for a certain period in the 'living/human world' and then in paradise.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese epitaph refers to Shi Jun/Wirkak as having a 'sacral intelligence of the mountains and peaks.'

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: See comment above

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Presumably, the three sons of the deceased were responsible for finding the scribe(s) to write, if not compose, the text.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The sarcophagus was plundered by grave robbers.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: Although the religious texts (particularly those relating to 'inner' ritual/liturgy) were traditionally recited by a hereditary male priesthood, it seems that women and children could learn the texts and engage in certain ritual activity at various times in the history of the religion. It is unlikely that women participated in the execution of the Sino-Sogdian epitaph under consideration, since none are mentioned other than Wirkak's wife.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: In the Chinese epitaph, it is the 'eminent distinction' and 'sacral intelligence' of Wirkak/Shi Jun which apparently leads to the (Sogdian) community recommending him to become "Chief of the Supervising Affairs Section of the Sabao (Bureau)" (Dien 2013 [2017], 105).

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No